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DOI:**ABSTRACT**

Immeasurably increases the role of information as a factor influencing economic growth, no less than the traditional factors in today's globalized economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the accelerated development of the system of global economic ties - capital and labor. In this regard, there are expanding and studies related to the phenomenon of "information economy" or "knowledge economy". All this poses the problem of information in any state of the economy, since its successful solution becomes one of the decisive conditions for the country's competitiveness. In this regard, in Kazakhstan in the first years of independent development of the state and industry information society program and the creation of a common information space have been taken. program "e-Government" is implemented in recent years.

KEYWORDS: Events, information macro economic governance system, manufacturing companies, personal computers, information technology, workflow, management decisions, on-farm reserves, mathematical methods, models, algorithms, optimal solutions.

INTRODUCTION

The main activities of these policy documents are reduced to the solution of priority tasks of macro-level of informatization of public administration economy, namely, the central and local authorities. And to a lesser degree of attention is paid to the same problems at the micro level of the economy, which includes primarily industrial enterprises, which are, in the meantime, the main element of the economy. Analysis of the processes of information obtained by the Agency for Statistics of the survey companies since 2004. It shows that these processes are mostly limited to the capacity of personal computers, to a lesser extent - software, even less effort aimed at education and training of specialists in the field of information technology. Computerization has been reduced to virtually automate certain aspects of management - accounting, workflow, monitoring, etc. A solution to the problem of informatization of enterprises involves the formation and development of information management systems that would allow on the basis of operational analysis and processing of information to make effective management decisions. In this formulation, the problem is solved before our individual businesses. The problem is compounded by the fact that, despite the presence in the scientific literature, a large number of publications devoted to the management and marketing organizations in enterprises, there is still no single view of the organization of their management on the principles of a systematic approach, providing complete coverage of all the factors that determine the processes of good governance. Thus, there is a distinct relationship between theoretical studies and

their implementation in a specific management practice. The development of economic theory and contemporary processes of globalization have led to the need to study the information resources [1]. Analysis of economic activity (Ahd) is an important element in the production management system, an effective means of identifying internal reserves, the basis of development of evidence-based planning and management decisions. An important methodological feature of the Ahd is the development and use of the system performance necessary for a comprehensive, systematic study of cause and effect relationships of economic phenomena and processes in the business enterprise. Thus, Ahd method is systematic, comprehensive study, measurement and generalization of influence of factors on the performance of the enterprise by processing special methods Plan Scorecard, accounting, reporting and other sources of information in order to increase production efficiency. Mathematical software includes mathematical methods, models, algorithms used in solving management problems. Software of economic ICs must be capable of effectively develop programs specific tasks, control the operation of the personal computer in the process of solving these problems, and to control the accuracy of their solutions. In a market economy the uncertainty of economic behavior of market participants is high enough. In this context of great practical importance acquire methods of prospective analysis, when it is necessary to make management decisions, assessing the situation and making possible a choice of several alternatives. Currently, on any matter technologically possible to gather so much information that no one can actually entered for the time to understand the situation, sometimes even just to see and even more efficient use. Hence the need for a systematic approach to the consideration of such large-scale events as the information processes [2].

For optimum performance usually take any profits made from the sale of products or the total load of all equipment groups. In our opinion, in the current realities of the complex nonlinear relationships between production processes like the use of optimization models is not only technically difficult, but not always effectively. On the other hand, if the company is diversified, the model becomes more cumbersome, which significantly affect the efficiency of data processing and obtaining analytical basis for decision-making [5].

Evaluation of maturity of enterprise management methodology can be carried out on the basis of the analysis:

- The composition and the relationship of the indicators used for monitoring business activities at different levels of the management hierarchy;
- Elaboration of management reporting forms and the procedure of its formation;
- The quality of a controller of financial flows;
- Completeness and quality regulations action services and job descriptions of employees for providing and processing information;
- The degree of automation control problems [7].

In modern conditions of effective management is needed as a tool for anticipating and overcoming the crisis of the enterprise development. In this regard, an important place in the scientific literature studies take on crisis management of enterprises, which implies specific requirements for information support prompt and effective solutions to the system. The need for the existence and improvement of crisis management, in the opinion of Kislukhin, due to the regularity of crisis phenomena in the socio-economic systems (including companies) who have, as you know, the cyclical nature of the development. In the economic literature there is no single universally accepted concept of crisis management and domestic economists are divided on the issue of the formation of its scientific concept. The reason lies in the different understanding of the essence of economists crisis management, its role and place in management theory and practice. At present, almost all countries of the world, because of their openness in the context of globalization, are experiencing a permanent transition from "old" to the so-called "new economy". But among the many researchers these processes, there is still no single prevailing point of view to understand the basics of forming a phenomenon that in the broad economic circles is called and the "new economy" and the "information economy" and "knowledge economy" and "knowledge society" etc [8]. Many economists are on the positions of the "knowledge economy." In their view, the world economy is growing with the increase in the intellectual component in the marketability of their products and services. According to experts, the share of new knowledge embodied in technological solutions, training of personnel, organization of production in developed countries accounts for 70-85% of GDP growth. The concept of the "new economy" is extremely difficult to reduce to any or most generalized single definition for this concept is multifaceted and is associated with a variety of functional and scientific fields. And, probably, the reduction of the phenomenon to a single definition is not quite

correct, because in the process of formulating the concept of limited descriptive himself a deep and multifaceted sense in this category may be lost. The only thing that can be noted with a greater or lesser degree of probability, that is what the new economy as an object of analysis and study is an open system with all the characteristics of the system properties (holistic, differentiation, negative entropy, cycling events, etc.). It is at the level of enterprises and various associations of producers of goods are competitive advantages of goods and formed their competitiveness, resulting from the general potential of the enterprise. Therefore, an important, but today, apparently, already the dominant direction of formation of competitive advantages of the company is to develop its effective development strategy. Most developers of information systems for government agencies are faced with the resistance of workers. Some systems, because it remains unused. To solve this problem is necessary, on the one hand, the rigid position of the leadership of organizations directly involved the first leaders in the creation and implementation of information systems, on the other hand - the constant explanatory work among employees, creation of motivation, aimed at the use of information systems [10].

For the successful application of information management systems important to the adequate software, which occupy a unique place construction model as the basis for the development and implementation of software products. This is largely due to the following aspects of business management. In a market economy the uncertainty of economic behavior of market participants is high enough. In this context of great practical importance acquire methods of prospective analysis for management decision-making, in the process of assessment of possible situations and the choice of many possible alternatives. Regarding the specific modeling tools, we can conclude that obviously can not be specific types of economic-mathematical model, which would be an adequate form suited for modeling the management functions of enterprises, since there are differences in their management attitudes and states of development. A typical approach is only possible for the individual functions (control, accounting, certain financial and accounting operations, etc.), but on their basis, of course, it is difficult to issue an information base, objectively suitable for making decisions about the company's development strategy [12].

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